

Weak AI and Strong Human Intelligence: Scaling Social Environment in E-Learning

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Abstract

Close-knit groups are used to increase motivation in e-learning. This method is difficult to scale because it requires educators who are competent in group dynamics.

We propose to use a decision support system that allows the teacher to spend less time on each of the groups.

Keywords

e-learning, group dynamics, psychology of small groups, AI, Interaction Equivalency Theorem

Introduction

Despite many advantages, distance learning has a few disadvantages, the main of which is low motivation of students: less than 10 percent of students complete their studies [1].

This problem has several solutions.

1. You can use blended learning, but it requires attendance and may not be suitable for all students.
2. Gamification – is very popular method, but if subject is complex, competitive or game elements cause excessive cognitive load, which reduces motivation [5].
3. If you students have a low level self-confidence, you can use error-less learning [2],[4].
4. You can use participatory learning in small close-knit distance groups. In such cases, the focus is on the interpersonal relationships of students.

This idea is based on the Interaction Equivalency Theorem [3], and this way is very promising, but difficult to scale, because requires a sufficiently large number of qualified teachers.

We propose to use a Decision support system to reduce the amount of time spent on each of the group.

Motivation in E-Learning

According to the Interaction Equivalency Theorem [3], for a high level of learning motivation, one of three interactions is necessary and sufficient: "student-content", "student-teacher", "student-student".

"Student-student" interaction looks the most promising for distance learning. Interest for subject is fickle, and charismatic teachers are relatively rare. This interaction involves a close-knit group in which knowledge raises the status of the participant.

The teacher does not need to be constantly present during the discussion. It is required to positively reinforce the desired action: discussion of the subject. Starting from a certain point, not every correct action will be rewarded - the reinforcement effect will continue.

It is not required to stop the off-topic discussion. Moderate flooding creates friendlier and more laid-back atmosphere.

The main problem is conflicts and bullying. Such situations act as a punishment, reducing learning motivation and causing the student to stop learning. The teacher should stop such situations.

Not every specialist can form a close-knit groups. This requires knowledge of the psychology of small groups and the ability to manage group dynamics. The training of qualified teachers is becoming a separate task requiring significant resources.

Decision Support System

To improve the efficiency of a teacher who leads e-learning groups, we propose to use a decision support system that includes several functional modules.

1. A module that searches for words seems to invective vocabulary and informs the instructor. The list of words can be supplemented by the teacher.

2. A module that counts the number of messages left by each student during the week, displays statistics for the teacher and stores data for all students for each course. This information is needed by the teacher to assess the involvement of students in the learning process.

3. AI module that can be trained to recognize conflicts. Usually, three parameters are required for diagnostics: the number of comments per unit of time, the number of participants, and the length of messages.

The module reads information from forum threads marked as conflicting and enters their parameters into a table. Based on the data collected, an assessment of the actual communication on the forum is made. The teacher receives a message about a possible conflict.

The system is currently under development. It is able to reduce the burden on the teacher and simplify the scaling of distance courses without losing the involvement of students.

References

1. What Harvard Business School Has Learned About Online Collaboration From HBX. Jan Hammond, V.G. Narayanan, and Bharat N. Anand. Harvard Business Review. April 14, 2015

<https://hbr.org/2015/04/what-harvard-business-school-has-learned-about-online-collaboration-from-hbx>

2. R. Brown, Getting students not to fear confusion (2012) Using these ideas for undergraduate teaching of mathematics!

<https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/182665/getting-students-to-not-fear-confusion/182912#182912>

3. The Interaction Equivalency Theorem. Terumi Miyazoe, Tokyo Denki University, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo. Terry Anderson, Athabasca University, Edmonton, Alberta. Journal of Interactive Online Learning, Volume 9, Number 2, Summer 2010. Volume 9, Number 2, Summer 2010

<https://www.ncolr.org/jiol/issues/pdf/9.2.1.pdf>

4. Mazur, J.E. (2006). Learning and behavior. 6th edition. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.

5. Sweller, John (April 1988). "Cognitive Load During Problem Solving: Effects on Learning". Cognitive Science. 12 (2): 257–285. CiteSeerX 10.1.1.459.9126.

6. Bond, C. F., & Titus, L. J. (1983). Social facilitation: A meta-analysis of 241 studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 94(2), 265–292.